

CEEC-TAC8

**BOOK
OF
ABSTRACTS**

Editors:
Andrei Rotaru
Anita Martinović Bevanda
Marina Marić
Rodica Daniela Carpen
Matko Erceg

C E E C - T A C 8

***8th Central and Eastern European Conference
on Thermal Analysis and Calorimetry***

***16-19 September 2025
Mostar, Bosnia and Herzegovina***

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Book of abstracts of the 8th Central and Eastern European Conference on Thermal Analysis and Calorimetry (CEEC-TAC8).

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Table of Contents

Organizers	5
List of Sponsors and Partners	7
Foreword	9
International Organizing Committee	11
Executive Organizing Committee	12
Honorary Committee	12
Scientific Committee	12
General Information	13
List of Award Plenary, Plenary and Invited Lecturers	13
Program	14
Sponsors: Advertisement	15
Award Plenary Lectures	19
Plenary Lectures	25
Invited Lectures	37
Oral Presentations 1	51
<i>Theory, Kinetics, Energetics, Materials Science and Engineering</i>	
Oral Presentations 2	73
<i>Calorimetry, Thermodynamics, Structural changes, Polymers, Nanomaterials and Organic Functional Systems</i>	
Poster Session 1	95
Poster Session 2	129
Poster Session 3	163
List of Participants	197

Organizers

**The 8th Central and Eastern European Conference
on Thermal Analysis and Calorimetry**

CEEC-TAC8

16-19 September 2025 – Mostar, Bosnia and Herzegovina

is organized by the:

**Central and Eastern European Committee for
Thermal Analysis and Calorimetry (CEEC-TAC)**

University of Mostar

Faculty of Science and Education, University of Mostar

Faculty of Humanities and Social Sciences, University of Mostar

University of Split

Faculty of Chemistry and Technology, University of Split

Institute of Physical Chemistry-Ilie Murgulescu

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Central and Eastern European Committee for
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Dear Participants at CEEC-TAC8 Conference,

Let us express our great pleasure to welcome you here in Mostar – Bosnia and Herzegovina, for attending the joint 8th Central and Eastern European Conference on Thermal Analysis and Calorimetry (CEEC-TAC8) and between 16th and 19st of September 2025; we thank very much to all of you for joining us! You were invited in Mostar, which is the fifth largest city of Bosnia and Herzegovina, but certainly the most beautiful one! Mostar is the capital of the Herzegovina-Neretva Canton and the capital of the Herzegovina Historical Region. Mostar is situated on the Neretva River; it was named after the bridge keepers (mostari) who guarded the Stari Most (Old Bridge) over the Neretva during the Ottoman era. The Old Bridge, a UNESCO World Heritage Site, commissioned by Suleiman the Magnificent in the 16th century, is one of Bosnia and Herzegovina's most visited landmarks, and is considered an exemplary piece of Islamic architecture in the Balkans. Mostar has architecturally noteworthy buildings in a wide range of styles. Historicist architectural styles reflected cosmopolitan interest and exposure to foreign aesthetic trends and were artfully merged with indigenous styles. Examples include the Italianate Franciscan church, the Ottoman Muslibegovica house, the Dalmatian Corovic House and an Orthodox church which was built as gift from the Sultan. The later 19th century residential houses are predominantly in neoclassical style.

The CEEC-TAC8 conference gathers now 147 registered participants from 26 countries, presenting a total number of 155 scientific works. Of those, 2 are Award Plenary Lectures (APL), 5 are Plenary Lectures (PL), 12 are Invited Lectures (IL), 2 Parallel Sessions of Oral Presentations – 40 contributions (OP) & 3 Sessions of Poster Presentation – 96 contributions (PS). Each session of oral presentations is comprised of 20 works, while each poster presentations includes 32 works.

At this edition, Awards will be offered to exceptional scientists: *i*) Prof. Dimitris Achilias from Greece (Distinguished TA&C Researcher in Central & Eastern Europe) and *ii*) Dr. Tadas Dambrauskas from Lithuania (Outstanding Young TA&C Researcher in Central & Eastern Europe).

We would like to express our thanks to the people who contributed and supported the organization of this event, especially to the members of the Honorary Committee, Scientific Committee, International Organizing Committee, National Associations for Thermal Analysis and Calorimetry from Central and Eastern European countries, Executive Organizing Committee, Central and Eastern European Committee for Thermal Analysis and Calorimetry, University of Mostar, Faculty of Science and Education (University of Mostar), Faculty of Humanistics and Social Sciences (University of Mostar), University of Split, Faculty of Chemistry and Technology (University of Split), Babeş-Bolyai University, Institute of Physical Chemistry-Ilie Murgulescu, and Committee for Thermal Science and Calorimetry of Bosnia and Herzegovina. We acknowledge the great support of our Sponsors: RoVI Thermal Analysis Consultancy (Bronze Sponsor), AstrineXLab (Bronze Sponsor), Altium (Bronze Sponsor), Linseis (Bronze Sponsor), and Elsevier (Exclusive Sponsor). A special acknowledgement has to be addressed to the *Journal of Thermal Analysis and Calorimetry*, *Ceramics International*, *Hybrid Advances* and *Thermal Advances*, where special issues will be dedicated to research papers of our conference.

The 4-day meeting is hosted at the Faculty of Humanistics and Social Sciences (Filozofski fakultet) of the University of Mostar (Sveučilište u Mostaru). The official language of the conference is English. University of Mostar is the second largest university in the country and the only Croatian language university in Bosnia and Herzegovina. It was founded in 1977 as the University "Dzemal Bijedic" of Mostar, but changed name in 1992. The university has ten faculties and one Academy of Fine Arts, with 50 majors, 46 specializations and 70 study groups.

We hope that you will enjoy the city during your stay at the CEEC-TAC8 conference, and that you will leave Mostar with the same good feelings and memories as those after attending the previous conferences. We expect that this conference will give you novel scientific and practical knowledge, and enrich you with a variety of new contacts.

Looking forward to seeing you at forthcoming thermal analysis and calorimetry conferences, and hopefully in 2027 for CEEC-TAC9!

Andrei Rotaru & Anita Martinović Bevanda
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Synthesis and Adsorption Performance of Magnetic Geopolymer Composites for the Removal of Manganese from Groundwater

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The provision of safe drinking water is one of the greatest challenges of our time. Drinking water resources often contain various components, such as metal ions, natural organic substances, and others. Manganese is an essential metal with a vital function in living organisms; however, the presence of manganese ions in water in high concentrations ($> 50 \mu\text{g/L}$) has a negative impact on health. An effective method for removing manganese ions from water is adsorption, using various materials as adsorbents. This study investigated the efficiency of applying innovative biofunctionalized magnetic geopolymer composites for the demanganization of groundwater. The demanganization of groundwater from the Novi Sad area, which contains a high concentration of Mn ions ($400 \mu\text{g/L}$), was carried out using biofunctionalized magnetic geopolymer composites based on kaolin. These composites were functionalized by adding tangerine peel extract. The synthesized composites were characterized by XRD, FTIR, TG, DSC, and SEM/EDS methods and subsequently used as adsorbents for the removal of Mn ions. The removal of Mn ions was carried out with 5 g/L of the composite for 1 hour. After 10 minutes of the process, a high efficiency of Mn ion removal was achieved (91%), reducing the Mn content in the water to $35 \mu\text{g/L}$. With increasing reaction time, there is no significant increase in process efficiency (up to 95%). It can therefore be concluded that the composite materials used have a high potential for use as adsorbents for water demanganization.

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[1] Aouan, B.; Alehyen, S.; Fadil, M.; El Alouani, M.; Saufi, H.; El Herradi, E.H.; El Makhoukhi, F.; Taibi, M. J. Environ. Manage. 2023, 338, 117853.

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[2] El Alouani, M.; Saufi, H.; Moutaoukil, G.; Alehyen, S.; Nematollahi, B.; Belmaghraoui, W.; Taibi, M. J. Environ. Chem. Eng. 2021, 9(2), 105095. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jece.2021.105095>.